

Deliverable A2.2

Systematic Use Case Assessment

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1. Background

1.1. General aim

The main aim of the use and needs assessment was to investigate the adoption and implementation of EMBED deliverables across different HEIs in Belgium and the Netherlands.¹

These deliverables of the original EMBED-project include:

- a reference model with dimensions and indicators explained: <https://embed.eadtu.eu/download/2470/European%20Maturity%20Model%20for%20Blended%20Education.pdf?inline=1>
- measurement instruments: <https://embed.eadtu.eu/working-with-embed>
- implementation guidelines and examples for practice: <https://embed.eadtu.eu/download/2517/EMBED%20implementation%20guidelines.pdf?inline=1>
- a MOOC “Making blended education work”: <https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/making-blended-education-work>

Additionally, the project partners wanted to identify effective practices and proven approaches that are to be incorporated into the EMBED+Hub in the later phases of the project (WP4).

1.2. Research questions

The overarching research question guiding this study was: "How and why have higher education institutions in Belgium and the Netherlands adopted and implemented the EMBED deliverables, and what were the resulting impacts on institutional, program, and course-level practices?".

In alignment with this overarching research question, the following sub-questions were explored:

1. What factors have influenced the adoption and implementation of EMBED deliverables at different levels (institution, program, course) within HEIs?
2. How do stakeholders perceive the benefits and challenges of using EMBED deliverables in their institutional contexts?
3. What variations exist in the ways different institutions implement EMBED, and what contextual factors influence these differences?

¹ Based on the pre-study it occurred that no other member states had been using EMBED (see Goeman, K. & Dijkstra, W. (in-press). *The European Maturity Model for Blended Education: A Retrospective and an Outlook for the Future*. Full paper presented at the Eden Annual Conference 2025, Bologna, 15-17 June 2025).

4. To what extent have the EMBED deliverables supported the development of mature blended learning practices within HEIs?
5. What emerging needs have been identified regarding blended teaching and education, and how can EMBED+ address these needs?
6. What institutional policies, support structures, and strategies are necessary to ensure the long-term sustainability of EMBED deliverables?

1.3. Method

The project team conducted semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, including instructional designers, program coordinators, educational advisors and support staff members (see Appendices).

These were selected from the list of the pre-project impact analysis and these were contacted by e-mail. Eventually, snowballing was applied – it was difficult to reach participants because they had changed jobs or anymore involved in the field of blended teaching/education. To ensure reliability and validity, different measures were taken. Multiple researchers contributed to data collection, analysis and interpretation while templates are used for the different research phases.

A semi-structured interview protocol (see the Appendices) was used alongside pre-testing, interviewers' briefing, member checking, and peer review. The interview protocol was refined as needed during the process. The interview protocol started with the *opening questions* (+/- 5 minutes) whose purpose is to set the stage for the conversation, build rapport, and gather general background information about the participant's role and involvement in the institution's blended learning initiatives. These questions provide context for the rest of the interview. The *transition questions* (+/- 15 minutes) are designed to move the conversation from general background information to a deeper exploration of the participant's involvement with the specific resources being evaluated, in this case, the EMBED deliverables. These questions help to contextualize the role of the participant within their institution's wider strategy and their personal engagement with EMBED resources. The core questions (+/- 15 minutes) aim to dig deeper into the participant's actual experiences with the EMBED deliverables. Other core questions are designed to identify the key features that participants value the most in the EMBED framework, next to the evolving needs of users regarding the EMBED deliverables. The closing questions (+/- 5 minutes) allow the participant to share lessons learned. Prompts and probes were integrated in the protocol.

A multiple case analysis was applied to identify recurrent themes, challenges, and actionable recommendations. This integrates within-case and cross-case findings to establish understanding of the conditions necessary for the successful implementation of blended practices in higher education (see deliverable A2.1. "Instrument Development" for more details).

2. Results

2.1. Use case 1

Context and role

Respondent 1 (R1) engaged with the EMBED deliverables primarily at the course level, acting as an instructor with continuity across semesters. His role allowed for iterative experimentation within institutional boundaries, but without direct influence over programme or institutional strategy. R1 approached blended learning development pragmatically, focusing on manageable, incremental improvements rather than comprehensive redesign or system-level change.

User Experience with EMBED and Implementation Issues

R1 used the EMBED measurement instruments (scan) to identify areas for improvement in blended course design. While initial scan results were not always fully acted upon, R1 emphasised the value of stepwise improvement, targeting one or two indicators per semester to support sustainable development. This approach reduced perceived pressure and increased feasibility for instructors working within existing constraints.

Rather than deploying the full set of EMBED deliverables, R1 applied the model selectively, supporting gradual maturity development at the course level. Institutional constraints—such as restrictive procurement policies, limited tool access, faculty resistance, and insufficient training opportunities—restricted broader adoption at programme and institutional levels (RQ1, RQ3). Despite these challenges, EMBED was perceived as valuable for structuring reflection and guiding actionable course-level improvements (RQ2).

Adaptations of EMBED Deliverables

R1 tailored EMBED materials to fit his course context and developed a custom EMBED chatbot within ChatGPT. Publicly available EMBED documents - including self-assessment instruments, the European Maturity Model, and implementation guidelines - were integrated into the chatbot to provide interactive, personalised guidance for instructors and managers.

The chatbot guides users through EMBED steps, helps identify current maturity levels, and suggests next actions, making the framework more accessible in daily practice. Initial testing revealed several improvement areas:

- the need for practical examples and testimonials to ground guidance in lived practice;
- clearer distinctions between maturity Levels 1, 2, and 3, as Level 3 was perceived as overly ambitious;
- managing expectations by positioning the chatbot as supportive guidance, not an authoritative source, given occasional inconsistencies and scope drift in an internet-connected environment.

These adaptations illustrate how local tooling can enhance usability and relevance while preserving EMBED's core intent.

Suggestions for EMBED+

R1 identified several priorities to strengthen adoption, usability, and sustainability:

- Structured scaffolding to prevent users from feeling overwhelmed, including step-by-step guidance, instructional videos, and clear explanations at each stage of the EMBED scan.
- Concrete examples of maturity in practice, especially clarifying what different maturity levels look like and how progression can be achieved incrementally.
- Integration of AI as a blended learning component, not only as a student support tool but as part of flipped or hybrid teaching models (RQ5).
- Improved feedback mechanisms and wider testing to validate tools such as the chatbot.
- Institutional support and policy alignment, particularly around procurement, tool access, and professional development (RQ6).
- Shared repositories and infrastructure, potentially coordinated by bodies such as SURF, to support scalable and sustainable adoption.

Overall, R1's case highlights how EMBED can effectively support incremental, instructor-led course improvement, while also underscoring the need for clearer scaffolding, achievable maturity pathways, and institutional enablers to sustain long-term impact.

2.2. Use case 2

Context and role

R2 engaged with EMBED primarily at the institutional level, focusing on shaping the internal quality framework and implementation processes for blended learning. She operated as a policy and framework developer, working across departments and stakeholder groups, rather than directly with courses or programme design. Her role involved translating EMBED concepts into the institution's context, aligning them with existing policy tools and organizational priorities, but without direct responsibility for teaching practice implementation.

User Experience with EMBED and Implementation Issues

EMBED was initially used as a reflective scaffold to guide discussions and inform institutional frameworks. While it clarified dimensions, provided a shared language, and stimulated reflection, practical uptake was constrained by competing frameworks (e.g., Van den Akker, "Bestemmingsplan" toolkits), overlapping initiatives, and resource-intensive processes. Programme- and course-level adoption stalled due to COVID-19 disruptions, competing priorities, and the model's English-language, research-oriented terminology, which clashed with the Dutch-speaking, applied-sciences context.

R2 valued EMBED as inspirational and structuring, but its perceived complexity and static deliverables limited direct usability for instructors and instructional designers. Implementation was partial: some dimensions informed institutional policy ("De <name of the HEI> kiest voor blended learning"), but broader integration and sustained use were limited by lack of follow-through and absence of a shared community of practice.

Adaptations of EMBED Deliverables

Positioned in Chung's Personalisation phase, R2 adapted EMBED to her institutional context, modifying language, culture, and organizational priorities. She emphasised the need for modular, editable, and context-sensitive versions of EMBED+, translating selected dimensions into actionable policy instruments.

R2 also advocated for a living repository of peer adaptations to enable institutions to learn from each other, reduce duplication, and foster ongoing professional dialogue. This approach reflects the application of EMBED as a strategic inspiration tool, rather than a fully implemented framework.

Suggestions for EMBED+

To enhance adoption and long-term relevance, R2 identified several key requirements for EMBED+:

- Integration of emerging priorities such as AI, VR/XR, and digital accessibility.
- Editable, open-source deliverables, e.g., Excel-based tools.
- Stakeholder-specific resources, including teacher checklists and leadership dashboards.
- Multilingual, context-sensitive templates to suit diverse institutional settings.
- A shared repository of adaptations and use cases to promote cross-institution learning.
- Sustained dissemination, via newsletters, webinars, and case studies.

- Formalised support structures, including dedicated staff, professional development, governance mechanisms, and communities of practice.

R2's case demonstrates how EMBED can support institutional reflection and policy development, but that scalable adoption requires adaptable, visible, and context-aware resources alongside dedicated support and ongoing professional engagement.

2.3. Use case 3

Context and role

R3 is actively engaged with the EMBED deliverables within a University of Applied Sciences, operating across course, programme, and institutional levels. His role spans hands-on course design, programme coherence work, and participation in institutional strategy discussions. Positioned at the Confirmation stage of implementation, R3 represents a sustained user of EMBED thinking, with experience in both practical application and strategic alignment. This multi-level involvement provides R3 with a comprehensive perspective on blended learning maturity within the institution.

User Experience with EMBED and Implementation Issues

At the course level, R3 used EMBED to enhance blended learning design by aligning face-to-face and online activities with course objectives. EMBED's emphasis on interaction, flexibility, inclusiveness, and study load alignment supported the creation of balanced, active, and student-centred learning experiences. At the programme level, R3 applied EMBED to assess coherence and alignment across courses, focusing on consistent use of blended tools and flexibility to improve the overall student learning experience. At the institutional level, R3 engaged with management and faculty to integrate EMBED into strategic planning, recognising that systemic implementation requires explicit institutional support beyond individual course initiatives.

Overall, EMBED supported reflective assessment of current practices, identification of growth areas, and the development of strategies to strengthen blended education maturity (RQ4). However, adoption varied across institutions and contexts, influenced by readiness, existing structures, and levels of strategic alignment (RQ3).

Adaptations of EMBED Deliverables

Rather than creating extensive structural modifications, R3 primarily adapted EMBED through contextualised application across levels. He emphasised the importance of combining top-down strategic support with bottom-up faculty initiatives to foster shared ownership. EMBED was used as a reflective framework to align practices, stimulate dialogue, and support continuous improvement, rather than as a rigid implementation tool.

R3 highlighted the need for practical examples of maturity in action to complement the conceptual framework, particularly to support institutions or teams with less developed blended practices.

Suggestions for EMBED+

R3 identified several priorities to strengthen adoption, implementation, and sustainability:

- Strengthening shared language to enable consistent discussions about blended learning across institutional levels (RQ1).
- Providing concrete examples and case studies that demonstrate what maturity looks like in practice, helping to overcome resistance to change (RQ2, RQ5).
- Supporting continuous reflection and professional dialogue, recognising that maturity thinking requires ongoing engagement.
- Fostering communities of practice to support peer learning and institutional alignment.

- Ensuring clear management positioning, combined with bottom-up initiatives, to bridge leadership and staff collaboration.
- Embedding EMBED within institutional policy, professional development, and support structures to ensure long-term sustainability (RQ6).

For sustainable scaling, R3 emphasised the importance of selecting pilot institutions that already show openness to innovation, shared maturity language, and aligned leadership. Co-creation between managers and educators, shared goal setting, and feedback mechanisms were identified as essential conditions for sustained blended education innovation.

Table 1*EMBED Use Experiences: Case by case analysis R1-R3*

Use case description	User experiences	Issues during implementation	Adaptations/Modifications
Use as a reflective framework and policy reference to discuss and align blended learning themes at institutional and program levels.	R1: Appreciated EMBED as conceptual framework for reflection and structuring discussion. R2: Found EMBED valuable as a "hook" for policy themes, but more at a conceptual level than practical use. R3: EMBED+ provided a shared language, fostering alignment across institutional, program, and course levels.	R1: Multiple competing frameworks caused confusion; limited translation to daily practice. R2: Organizational inertia; no formal implementation; lack of clear guidance for different stakeholder groups. R3: EMBED's comprehensiveness and complexity made direct implementation challenging without substantial interpretation and translation work.	R1: Partial personalization blending EMBED with local models. R2: No full implementation, but informal use as conceptual support. R3: Institutions selectively adapted and translated the model to fit their local contexts, ambitions, and existing structures, ensuring it aligned with their unique priorities.
Use for supporting personalization and professional development of teaching staff, including feedback loops and identifying positions on maturity.	R1: Mixed to positive on usefulness; need clearer "how-to" guides for different roles (teachers, designers, management). R2: Expressed desire for personalized tools; found model useful to adapt for local context and personalization of learning approaches. R3: EMBED+ was valued as a complete, structured framework that fosters reflection, shared understanding, and alignment among stakeholders across institutional, program, and course levels.	R1: Limited training and support; some resistance from faculty due to complexity. R2: Lack of infrastructure support; difficulty adapting materials due to format (e.g., PDFs not editable); need for more accessible materials. R3: Barriers such as time constraints, tool rigidity (e.g., non-editable PDFs), and a lack of momentum for implementation were decisive.	R1: Requested editable, adaptable resources; wished for shared repository of adapted models. R2: Made informal adaptations; personalized EMBED elements for institution's use but no formal rollout. R3: institution developed framework and strategy based on EMBED.
Use as input for institutional decision-making and strategic planning on blended learning offerings.	R1: Saw value for boards and steering groups to assess maturity and identify strategic priorities. R2: Also viewed EMBED as useful for institute-level reflection but noted lack of momentum for actual implementation. R3: EMBED helped foster strategic consensus and initial faculty engagement. It prompted insightful vision-setting and reflective discussions.	R1: Competing priorities and lack of responsibility slowed uptake. R2: Organizational inertia; no concrete steps to embed EMBED in decision-making. R3: Systematic advancement toward mature blended learning remained limited. Faculty-level pockets of activity exist, but broader, sustained practice change is uneven.	R1 & R2: No significant modifications; EMBED remains a reference framework rather than an actively implemented policy tool. R3: EMBED was used for strategic exploration and framework development; practical follow-through into consistent implementation remains a challenge.

2.4. Use case 4

Context and role

R4 has been deeply involved in blended education since his early teaching career and later in his official role within the Education Department of a Dutch University of Applied Sciences. Long before COVID-19, he acted as a passionate advocate and hands-on practitioner of blended teaching. His approach evolved through two phases: an initial phase centred on experimenting with educational technologies, followed by a COVID-era shift toward pedagogically grounded blended teaching, emphasising instructional design over tool adoption. R4's role combined personal expertise with institutional responsibility, positioning him as both a change agent and strategic facilitator across multiple organisational levels.

User Experience with EMBED and Implementation Issues

R4 used the EMBED model and its deliverables across course, programme, and institutional levels. At the course level, EMBED-informed tools and templates supported lesson design, helping teachers map synchronous and asynchronous activities and improve instructional coherence. At the programme level, R4 coordinated an eight-programme faculty-wide initiative, embedding EMBED into structured workflows including maturity scans, goal setting, workshops, annual action plans, and review cycles grounded in zero-based measurements and the PDCA approach. At the institutional level, EMBED informed the development of tools such as ActiTool, supported digital maturity scans, and guided strategic planning discussions related to quality assurance and faculty development.

EMBED's utility lay in replacing fragmented, tool-driven practices with structured, systemic integration. It enabled shared goal-setting, reflective dialogue, and alignment between management, instructional designers, and academic staff (RQ1). However, variation in uptake reflected contextual factors such as faculty autonomy, staff digital readiness, strategic alignment, and the presence of champions or early adopters (RQ3). Users also reported challenges related to EMBED's breadth, steep learning curve, and lack of role-specific guidance, as well as limited adaptability of static formats such as large PDF documents (RQ2).

Adaptations of EMBED Deliverables

R4's team embedded EMBED deeply into institutional processes, using the maturity instrument as a backbone for progression from ad-hoc experimentation to structured implementation. Through baseline ("nulpunt") measurements, ambition setting, and annual evaluation cycles, the team advanced blended learning maturity to the mastery stage at programme scale.

The EMBED framework supported regular assessment, planning, and review cycles, enabling systematic improvement. However, later stages—personalisation and confirmation—were less fully embedded. Alignment with broader PDCA-based quality assurance mechanisms remains an area for consolidation to fully institutionalise maturity thinking.

Suggestions for EMBED+

Drawing on extensive implementation experience, R4 proposed several enhancements to strengthen EMBED+:

- Modularisation of resources to shorten the learning curve, including microlearning units and lightweight digital versions tailored to course-, programme-, and institutional-level users.
- Integration of practical lesson-design tools, such as templates for constructive alignment, synchronous/asynchronous blending, scaffolding for self-regulation, and student motivation.
- Clearer maturity rubrics, with role-specific indicators (e.g. what Level 2 means concretely at course level) and facilitated work sessions to translate indicators into practice.
- Embedding AI references within pedagogical indicators, linking emerging technologies to technology-enhanced pedagogies rather than isolating AI as a standalone dimension.

2.5. Use case 5

Context and role

R5 works as an instructional designer at the Teaching and Learning Service (TLS) of a research-based university. Her professional engagement has recently expanded from course-level support to programme-level involvement. She operates within a central support unit, facilitating pedagogical innovation but without direct authority over institutional policy or governance. R5 acts as a bridge between instructors, programme directors, and institutional initiatives, supporting both hands-on course design and exploratory programme-level adoption.

User Experience with EMBED and Implementation Issues

At the course level, EMBED is actively used in multi-day design bootcamps. It guides reflection during initial course design and is revisited mid-process to refine course drafts. Practitioners reached maturity in design through these structured, hands-on sessions.

At the programme level, EMBED use was exploratory. TLS piloted a programme-level reflection instrument with programme directors, generating strong interest but limited follow-through. Institutional maturity is emerging, characterised by dialogue rather than systematic embedding. Implementation challenges include the model's complexity, lack of explicit guidance, and the gap between practitioner interest and institutional incentives (RQ2, RQ1). Contextual factors influencing adoption include unit-level adaptation, pedagogical autonomy, absence of institutional policy, and lack of binding timelines or incentives.

Adaptations of EMBED Deliverables

R5 and her team customised EMBED templates to reflect programme-specific needs such as accessibility, monitoring, and inclusivity, ensuring alignment with local workflows. These adaptations foster ownership and stronger uptake. Course-level implementation relied on practical facilitation and educator-centric scaffolds, while programme-level implementation remained conceptual and idea-driven. TLS emphasized localized, domain-specific diagnostics and adaptable templates to bridge the gap between isolated course improvements and broader curriculum transformation.

Emerging innovations included modular tools (templates, microlearning), resource hubs with CC-licensed materials, and structured pathways to translate interest into actionable programme-level interventions (RQ5).

Suggestions for EMBED+

R5 highlighted several priorities for EMBED+ to enhance adoption, usability, and sustainability:

- Provide adaptable, domain-specific diagnostics and templates to support programme-level adaptation.
- Embed EMBED within quality assurance, curriculum planning, incentives, and governance mechanisms.
- Integrate funding models, policy drivers, and scheduling cycles to facilitate structured follow-through (RQ6).

- Offer modular resources such as microlearning units, action-oriented programme pathways, and reusable CC-licensed materials.
- Support a bridge between practitioner engagement and structural embedding, ensuring conceptual buy-in translates into systematic adoption.

Overall, R5's case illustrates that EMBED effectively supports structured, course-level innovation, while programme- and institutional-level adoption requires local tailoring, facilitation, and policy alignment to achieve sustainable impact.

2.6. Use case 6

Context and role

R6's role emerged from urgent institutional needs during the COVID-19 pandemic at a Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences. Positioned as an educational advisor with strong hands-on responsibilities, R6 focused on direct teacher support through one-on-one coaching, workshops, and policy drafting. In parallel, she developed an internal faculty webpage documenting room types, technical setups, and best practices for high-quality hybrid teaching. Her work was primarily situated at the faculty and course levels, rather than within institutional leadership or programme governance.

User Experience with EMBED and Implementation Issues

EMBED adoption was driven by pandemic-related urgency and advisor initiative. Uptake was uneven: while pilots were successful at the course level, broader scaling was limited by lecturer fatigue, competing demands, fragmented technological literacy, and decentralised ownership structures (RQ1). EMBED use remained faculty-based rather than institutional or programmatic.

R6 is positioned in the Adjustment phase, actively customising EMBED tools based on feedback and embedding them into course-level routines, but without having reached mastery or institutional standardisation. Engagement challenges included low lecturer response rates, vague terminology, high perceived time investment, and varying levels of readiness (RQ3). Participation in the EMBED MOOC supported advisor reflection, but lecturers experienced it as too lengthy and academic.

Despite these barriers, EMBED provided a shared framework that helped structure reflection and local initiatives.

Table 2
R6's User experiences and suggestions for EMBED+

Use case description	User experiences	Implementation issues	Adaptations of EMBED deliverables	Suggestions for EMBED+
Course-level maturity assessment and spider diagram	R6 used spider visualization for reflective analysis across seven dimensions	Low lecturer response rate; vague terminology; time burden; varying user readiness	Developed a detailed questionnaire; shared openly via Qualtrics	Automate spider generation; streamline questions; tiered access
MOOC participation	Advisors personally gained background; fostered reflection	Approximation by lecturers; MOOC too lengthy/academic	N/A	Offer short audiovisual snippets and practical guides
Inclusiveness and accessibility integration	Recognize AI and access needs; maintain broad definition	Lack of illustrative tech-aware examples	N/A	Add real-world exemplars to inclusivity dimension
Structural resources awareness	Inventory of campus infrastructure raised faculty awareness	Limited faculty knowledge hampering use	N/A	Embed infrastructure maps and facilities guides within toolkit
Study load and self-regulation	Positive integration of scheduled self-study supports learner autonomy	Not previously tracked or supported structurally	N/A	Add as distinct subdimension; provide scheduling templates and rubrics

Adaptations of EMBED Deliverables

R6 and a colleague adapted the EMBED spider diagram into a detailed Qualtrics-based questionnaire to assess course-level blended maturity across the seven EMBED dimensions. This enabled deeper reflection but remained confined to small-scale experimentation.

Additional adaptations included:

- Scheduled self-study blocks embedded into course timetables (e.g. e-module afternoons, recorded lectures), supporting student self-regulation and flexibility for working students.
- Infrastructure mapping, inventorying recording studios, equipment loans, and classroom types. While faculty awareness remained limited, embedding these inventories into existing resources helped lower access barriers.
- Inclusivity framing, maintaining EMBED's broad definition while recognising emerging AI and accessibility needs.

R6 also shared an open-access version of the self-developed maturity assessment tool with the EMBED+ team, signalling commitment to shared development and reuse.

Suggestions for EMBED+

R6 identified several priorities for EMBED+ to achieve sustained impact (RQ2):

- Tiered resources: quick-entry materials complemented by deeper, optional guidance.
- Tool automation: automated spider diagrams, dashboards, and streamlined questionnaires.
- Clear and relatable terminology to reduce abstraction and cognitive load.
- Concise professional development formats, such as short audiovisual snippets and practical guides instead of long MOOCs.
- Expanded dimensions and examples, particularly for AI literacy, sustainability, digital equity, study load balance, and data-informed reflection.
- Integration into QA cycles and PD, ensuring EMBED use becomes routine rather than optional.
- Embedded infrastructure guidance, making facilities and technical options visible and actionable.
- Peer-led champion strategies and incentives to counter fatigue and stimulate adoption.

Overall, R6's case highlights how EMBED can support meaningful course-level innovation under pressure, while also revealing the limits of scalability without simplification, automation, and structural embedding.

2.7. Use case 7

Context and role

According to R7, from an institutional leadership perspective, EMBED served as a practical lever to secure expertise and align long-term strategy. Blended education at R7's HEI has evolved significantly, entering a new phase in which issues such as digital sovereignty and sustained ecosystems have become central. This shift signals that EMBED must evolve into EMBED+ to remain relevant in a changing institutional landscape.

COVID-19 acted as a catalyst, accelerating institutional interest in blended formats. Nevertheless, faculty conservatism and a degree of “blended fatigue” emerged over time, and the absence of structural incentives limited programme-wide scaling.

User Experience with EMBED and Implementation Issues

R7 used EMBED strategically to persuade institutional leadership to invest in blended learning support and to align long-term planning. By applying the innovation-decision taxonomy, R7 reached the Personalisation phase: EMBED was internalised, reshaped, and consistently applied to fit the institution's specific context (R4).

At the HEI level, progress was strongest in planning and team structuring, indicating considerable maturity. In contrast, analytics usage and formal governance structures remained underdeveloped. Implementation varied across organisational layers: EMBED was explicit at institutional leadership and departmental levels, but less formalised at programme and course levels, where it was often used implicitly without attribution.

The institution's distributed autonomy required local adaptations, while fragmented organisational cultures slowed policy uptake (R3). Although a few strong champions enabled institutional persuasion, the lack of structural incentives constrained broader adoption (R1).

Adaptations of EMBED Deliverables

R7 modified and adapted EMBED to fit his institution's strategic decision-making structures, weaving the model into leadership forums and persuasive narratives rather than using it solely as a descriptive framework.

Users valued EMBED's shared language, visual clarity, and strategic planning prompts. At the same time, they highlighted challenges including implicit usage, gaps in data governance, the absence of AI considerations, and unclear role structures (R2). R7 stressed the importance of data-supported decision-making for improving blended courses, noting that course designers require training in analytics tools, while institutional leaders need clear strategic roadmaps.

Suggestions for EMBED+

To drive further adoption and implementation of mature blended practices, R7 identified several critical issues:

- Strategic alignment: embed EMBED tools, metrics, and language directly within institutional strategy.
- Recognition and incentives: introduce awards and incentives to empower faculty champions and reinforce cultural change.

- Resourcing: allocate dedicated budgets for personnel, training, and analytics infrastructure.
- Focus on innovators: concentrate implementation efforts on early adopters and enthusiastic faculties as change agents.
- Strategic advocacy: use EMBED frameworks for persuasion, not only for description, to justify strategic change.
- Conscious embedding of tools: integrate rubrics, spider diagrams, templates, and workshops into QA processes to ensure visible and reproducible usage.

Emerging needs identified by R7 include analytics literacy, AI policy awareness (particularly ethics and governance), and digital sovereignty with clear stewardship of platforms and data.

Regarding sustainability strategies for EMBED+ (RQ6), R7 emphasized:

- Clarifying terminology to avoid conflating unrelated challenges.
- Expanding the Facilities dimension to include AI policy, data governance, and digital sovereignty, potentially introducing a fourth 'sovereign' maturity level.
- Establishing a formal product owner role within Governance, with clear responsibilities, funding, and institutional positioning.
- Prioritising visual clarity through simple diagrams, complemented by role-based playbooks and senior-leader co-creation.
- Defining data-centric maturity by embedding learning analytics routines into QA and PD cycles.

By adopting these recommendations, EMBED+ can evolve from a static model into a living framework.

Finally, R7 recommended sharing the following materials via the EMBED+ ResourcesHUB:

- A CC-licensed repository on developing online and blended education.
- A local adaptation model of the EMBED framework used at his HEI.
- A series of institutional reports on blended teaching aligned with EMBED.

2.8. Use case 8

Context and role

Respondent 8 (R8) is a programme manager at a Centre for Teaching and Learning, at a university of applied sciences. R8's started as a secondary school teacher, later transitioning into teacher training and educational innovation. R8's interest in blended education emerged from early classroom experiments integrating digital tools to enhance student engagement. This led to a broader focus on personalized and differentiated learning supported by technology.

In 2018, R8 stepped down as programme coordinator for teacher training to lead the Dutch “Werkplaats Onderwijs Leertechnologie”, a university initiative supporting educational innovation through funding and coaching. During the COVID-19 pandemic, R8 played a key role in scaling blended learning efforts, culminating in the development of the BLEND-HR programme. Under R8's leadership, support structures for blended education were formalised, including the appointment of blended learning advisors and coaches.

R8 was also actively involved in the Acceleration Plan for Educational Innovation (The Netherlands), particularly within the field of teacher PD.

User Experience with EMBED and Implementation Issues

In this context, R8 was introduced to the EMBED model, which R8 used in combination with the Bewegingssensor tool to assess institutional maturity in blended education. EMBED accelerated institutional maturity across a three-year period (2021–2024). R8's journey exemplifies how EMBED facilitated large-scale strategic alignment.

The spider diagrams anchored strategy, while programme-level design adapted the model practically (RQ4). EMBED succeeded in clarifying institutional maturity and galvanizing leadership. The divergent maturity assessments uncovered in board-level workshops proved crucial in setting new digitization agendas.

However, uptake varied across levels: while institutional and programme levels embraced EMBED as a conversation-starter, course-level integration remained sporadic (RQ3).

Adaptations of EMBED Deliverables

R8 has moved beyond experimentation to the Adjustment phase; R8 actively used, modified and contextualized the model for her institution:

- Combined EMBED with the “Bewegingssensor” tool: the spider-diagram maturity framework from EMBED was combined with an internal organizational change tool (called the “Bewegingssensor”) to facilitate reflective conversations during Board of Directors sessions. This combination helped clarify differing perceptions of maturity and guided strategic decision-making at the institutional level.
- Integrated EMBED into programme-level design sessions: R8 and her team embedded EMBED maturity discussions into ABC Learning Design workshops. They used EMBED to define programme-level maturity goals and followed through with ABC methods to develop the required course components.

Suggestions for EMBED+

R8 indicated that EMBED's visual spider-diagrams, shared language, and framework for structured reflection are valued. These tools helped align stakeholders and clarified

strategic positioning. Yet, the model's high-level abstraction hindered deep engagement. Questions emerged around subdimensional clarity, especially regarding institutional resources, layered support, financing, and future-facing capabilities like AI readiness, demonstrating common friction points between conceptual appeal and concrete application (RQ2).

R8 emphasized the importance of adding AI awareness, change readiness, finance alignment with pedagogical needs, and integrated support layers (student, instructor, central services, faculties).

Sustainability requirements for EMBED+

- Governance & leadership buy-in, visible through strategy sessions and board-level tools.
- Layered institutional support, subdividing technical and educational aid at faculty and student levels.
- Clear digital change skill frameworks, beyond conventional technical training.
- Financial alignment with pedagogical goals, ensuring resources support practical innovation.
- Toolkits & resource bundles, including slides, a crosswalk between EMBED and pedagogical tools, model customization guides, and embedding into essential practices like QA and PD.

3. Synthesis and recommendations

3.1. Overview of use cases

Table 3 presents an overview of the eight use cases, summarizing respondents' roles, levels of engagement with EMBED, key experiences and adaptations, implementation challenges, and suggestions for EMBED+. This overview provides contextual grounding for the cross-case analysis by research question presented in Section 3.2.

Table 3
Overview of use cases

Use case	Context and role	Key experiences and adaptations	Implementation challenges	Suggestions for EMBED+
R1	Course-level teacher support; pilot adopter	Hands-on support, course redesign, MOOC participation	Low engagement, technical literacy gaps	Short guides, tiered resources, clear visuals
R2	Programme-level coordination	Used spider diagrams for reflection; embedded into PD	Limited cross-program uptake, varying readiness	Automate tools, add scheduling and planning templates
R3	Department-level lead	Facilitated team workshops; used EMBED for QA	Inconsistent terminology, faculty fatigue	Integrate into QA, peer champions, data dashboards
R4	Faculty-level innovation	Customised EMBED for blended courses	Fragmented uptake, lack of incentives	Governance roles, structured incentives, toolkits
R5	Central service support	Supported tech adoption and faculty reflection	Resistance to change, scattered infrastructure	Embed AI awareness, data literacy, inclusive examples
R6	Faculty of Medicine & Health Sciences; hands-on advisor	Developed Qualtrics questionnaire, self-study blocks, infrastructure mapping	Low lecturer response, time burden, vague terms	Tiered resources, automation, clear terminology, QA integration, peer champions, AI/sustainability inclusion
R7	Institutional leader	Secured expertise, aligned strategy, promoted champions	Distributed autonomy, faculty fatigue, implicit usage, missing data governance	Strategic alignment, incentives, dedicated resources, Product Owner role, QA integration, AI policy, digital sovereignty, visual clarity, learning analytics
R8	Large-scale institutional alignment	Combined EMBED with organizational change tools, programme-level integration	Sporadic course-level uptake, high abstraction, gaps in AI readiness, layered support, finance	Leadership buy-in, layered support, digital change skills, financial alignment, toolkits/resource bundles, QA/PD integration, AI awareness

3.2. Cross-case analysis by research question

3.2.1. What factors have influenced the adoption and implementation of EMBED deliverables at different levels (institution, program, course) within HEIs?

The adoption and implementation of EMBED deliverables across higher education institutions (HEIs) were influenced by a combination of institutional, programme, and course-level factors. At the institutional level, alignment with strategic priorities, leadership commitment, and the presence of champions or early adopters emerged as critical enablers (R3, R4, R7, R8). Competing initiatives or pre-existing frameworks sometimes fragmented attention and slowed adoption (R2). At the programme level, adoption was facilitated by structured drivers and enablers, professional autonomy, and unit-level engagement, while barriers included limited mandate or lack of binding incentives (R5, R7).

At the course level, instructor engagement, continuity across semesters, and manageable workloads were central, whereas time constraints, faculty fatigue, and variable technical literacy limited uptake (R1, R6, R7). Across all levels, local tailoring, scaffolding, and alignment with existing workflows significantly enhanced adoption and usability.

3.2.2. How do stakeholders perceive the benefits and challenges of using EMBED deliverables in their institutional contexts?

Stakeholders widely recognized EMBED's value in providing a shared language for blended learning, supporting structured reflection, and aligning practices across courses, programmes, and institutional strategies (R2, R3, R4, R5, R7, R8). The deliverables were appreciated for enabling goal-setting, reflective professional development, and evidence-informed course design (R1, R5, R6). However, challenges were consistently noted, including the model's complexity, high abstraction, and steep learning curve (R2, R4, R5, R6, R7). Users also reported gaps in role-specific guidance and difficulties translating conceptual frameworks into actionable steps, particularly in contexts lacking institutional mandates or structural support.

3.2.3. What variations exist in the ways different institutions implement EMBED, and what contextual factors influence these differences?

Implementation of EMBED varied considerably across institutions and levels. Course-level adoption was largely hands-on and incremental, led by individual instructors or instructional designers, and often supported through bootcamps, templates, and guided reflection tools (R1, R5, R6). Programme-level adoption was typically exploratory and dependent on facilitation and partial alignment with programme governance structures (R5, R7, R8). Institutional-level adoption required explicit leadership support, strategic integration, and alignment with quality assurance and governance processes (R2, R3, R4, R7, R8). Key contextual factors explaining these variations included faculty autonomy, institutional culture, digital readiness, and resource availability.

3.2.4. To what extent have the EMBED deliverables supported the development of mature blended learning practices within HEIs?

EMBED deliverables contributed to the development of mature blended learning practices at multiple levels. At the course level, iterative use of maturity scans, guided reflections, and practical scaffolds supported incremental improvements (R1, R5, R6). At the programme level, EMBED facilitated alignment of learning objectives, course coherence, and structured programme reflection (R5, R7, R8). At the institutional level, the model supported strategic planning, leadership alignment, and policy discussions that fostered systemic adoption (R2, R3, R4, R7, R8). Across cases, course-level maturity was generally achieved more rapidly, whereas programme- and institutional-level embedding often remained partial, constrained by policy gaps or insufficient structural support.

3.2.5. What emerging needs have been identified regarding blended teaching and education, and how can EMBED+ address these needs?

Respondents identified several emerging needs to guide the development of EMBED+:

- Integration of AI, VR/XR, and other emerging technologies to enhance blended teaching (R1, R4, R6, R7).
- Editable, modular, and context-sensitive deliverables for diverse roles, including leadership dashboards, instructor checklists, and templates for programme staff (R2, R5, R6).
- Short, role-specific learning modules and practical examples to reduce complexity and support adoption (R4, R5, R6).
- Shared repositories and communities of practice to disseminate local adaptations, reduce duplication, and foster peer learning (R2, R6, R7).
- Integration of analytics and evidence-informed tools for continuous improvement (R7).

3.2.6. What institutional policies, support structures, and strategies are necessary to ensure the long-term sustainability of EMBED deliverables?

Sustainable implementation of EMBED requires a combination of strategic, structural, and community-level supports. Critical enablers include visible leadership buy-in, clear alignment with institutional priorities, and the creation of dedicated roles or champions to maintain momentum (R3, R4, R7, R8). Continuous professional development, dedicated budgets, and access to tools and infrastructure are essential to support faculty and programme-level adoption (R1, R2, R6, R7). Embedding EMBED into quality assurance, curriculum planning, and governance structures ensures its integration beyond pilot initiatives (R4, R5, R7, R8). Finally, fostering peer networks, shared repositories, and communities of practice strengthens long-term sustainability and facilitates knowledge transfer across institutions (R2, R6, R7).

3.3. Cross-case synthesis table

Table 4 provides a consolidated overview of the cross-case findings across all six research questions. “Level of adoption” indicates where EMBED deliverables were primarily applied (course, programme, or institutional). “Practices” describe how respondents operationalized EMBED within their contexts. “Adoption phase” reflects each case’s position within Chung’s implementation model (Adjustment, Personalization, Confirmation, Mastery). Finally, the “RQ columns” synthesize case-specific insights per research question, highlighting patterns and variations across institutional levels.

Table 4
Cross-case synthesis table

Use Case	Level(s) of Adoption*	Practices	Adoption Phase	RQ1	RQ2	RQ3	RQ4	RQ5	RQ6
R1	Course	Customized chatbot; selective use of EMBED scans; incremental focus on 1-2 indicators	Adjustment / iterative course-level improvements	Instructor autonomy; institutional space to experiment; limited resources	Benefits: structured reflection, actionable guidance. Challenges: overwhelming breadth, lack of follow-up	Course-level adoption strongest; program/institutional uptake limited due to procurement & policy	Supported incremental, manageable course improvements	AI integration, practical examples/testimonials, scaffolding for stepwise use	Institutional support for tools; ongoing PD; structured scaffolding; shared repositories
R2	Institutional	Partial translation into internal quality & implementation frameworks; adapted language & dimensions	Personalization / strategic adaptation	Institutional priorities; competing frameworks; resource constraints	Benefits: shared language, structured reflection. Challenges: complexity, lack of direct usability	Institutional uptake influenced by competing initiatives, context, and language	Supported reflection & framework alignment; limited practical course/program adoption	Editable, modular tools; peer adaptation repository; multilingual & context-sensitive templates; AI/VR/XR	Leadership support; dedicated staff; communities of practice; professional development; policy alignment
R3	Course, Program, Institutional	EMBED scans, reflection tools; integrated into strategic planning; collaborative goal-setting	Confirmation / sustained use & embedding	Top-down support; bottom-up initiatives; shared language; practical examples	Benefits: shared understanding, alignment across levels. Challenges: resistance to change, continuous reflection required	Context-dependent variation in uptake; readiness & institutional culture influence adoption	Strengthened mature blended practices at all levels	Detailed case studies, communities of practice, ongoing PD resources	Policies supporting blended practices; continuous PD; leadership alignment; structured feedback & collaboration
R4	Course, Program, Institutional	ActiTool; maturity scans; PDCA-based annual cycles; lesson design templates	Mastery at programme-level; partial personalization/confirmation	Personal passion; leadership & funding support; faculty autonomy; early adopters	Benefits: shared language, structured planning, reflective cycles. Challenges: steep learning curve, rigid formats	Adoption influenced by faculty autonomy, digital readiness, strategic alignment	Advanced course/program maturity; systemic integration; institutional-level adoption partial	Modular, digital microlearning; lesson-design templates; clearer rubrics; AI integration in pedagogy	Leadership buy-in; policy alignment; embedding in QA; PD; structured planning cycles

R5	Course, Program	Custom templates for accessibility & inclusivity; programme-level reflection instrument; bootcamps	Course-level maturity; programme-level exploratory	Unit-level adaptation; pedagogical autonomy; lack of institutional mandates/incentives	Benefits: structured reflection, shared language. Challenges: conceptual complexity, delayed programmatic uptake	Course-level structured; programme-level exploratory; policy & institutional embedding limited	Hands-on course improvement; exploratory programme alignment	Adaptable, domain-specific templates; microlearning; bridging course-program adoption gap	QA embedding; curriculum alignment; incentives; governance; facilitation support
R6	Course	Course-level maturity assessment; spider diagram; self-study integration; MOOC participation	Adjustment / course-level customization	Faculty-level support; urgent COVID needs; technical literacy; workload	Benefits: reflective analysis, autonomy support. Challenges: low engagement, vague terminology, high time investment	Course-level adoption strong; faculty-level focus; programme/institutional limited	Enhanced reflection & course-level practices; maturity limited to small-scale experimentation	Tiered resources; automation of spider-diagrams; practical examples for inclusivity & accessibility	Embedded infrastructure guidance; PD support; peer champions; scalable templates
R7	Program, Institutional	Adapted EMBED deliverables; strategic forums; early adopters; persuasion tools	Personalization / active contextual adaptation	Leadership support; distributed autonomy; faculty champions; COVID acceleration	Benefits: shared language, strategic planning prompts. Challenges: implicit usage, missing governance & data structures	Program-level explicit, course-level implicit; uptake varied by faculty & culture	Supported strategic programmatic alignment; partial course-level adoption	Analytics literacy; AI policy; digital sovereignty; product owner roles; visual clarity	Embed in QA & PD cycles; structured incentives; resourcing; strategic advocacy
R8	Program, Institutional	EMBED + Bewegungssensor; program-level ABC Learning Design integration; board workshops	Adjustment / active customization & contextual use	Leadership & strategic alignment; institutional maturity; coaching & support structures	Benefits: clarified maturity, galvanised leadership. Challenges: high-level abstraction, subdimension clarity	Program & institutional alignment strong; course-level uptake sporadic	Facilitated institutional & program-level strategic maturity; partial course-level embedding	AI awareness, finance alignment, layered support; toolkits & resources; embedding into QA & PD	Governance buy-in; layered support; digital change skill frameworks; financial alignment; structured toolkits & resource bundles

3.4. Critical reflections

The interviews provided valuable insights into the adoption and implementation of the EMBED deliverables within higher education institutions (HEIs), on all three levels. The results highlight the multifaceted approach required for the successful implementation of maturity thinking in blended education. For the project, the interviews' findings are invaluable in guiding the development of the model, the matrix and the repository of resources.

The interview data reveal that while the model holds significant strategic potential, its usability varies when users engage with its deliverables. Fundamentally, EMBED+ is valued as a reflective framework that promotes shared understanding. Participants found it particularly effective in defining thematic priorities and shaping dialogue, often serving as a catalyst for conversations about blended learning, teaching, and education. The interview data further affirm EMBED's role in creating strategic consensus and initiating faculty-level engagement through reflective discussions and vision-setting. Yet, transformative, institution-wide blended learning remains elusive: most advancements are seen in localized pockets rather than sustainable change.

At the course level, the model's value is evident - such as using EMBED to set redesign objectives and then employing models or design principles to enact those changes. From initial analysis through iteration and refinement, EMBED has been applied to varying degrees. However, broader uptake depends on reducing friction in day-to-day use. To scale, EMBED's tools must be editable and lightweight, and they need to consistently suggest clear, actionable next steps. Furthermore, for EMBED+ to remain robust and relevant, it must evolve alongside emerging educational challenges, such as AI, sustainability, and equity. This means dynamically updating both the content of the model and the support structures surrounding it.

Nevertheless, a persistent tension emerged: the model's comprehensiveness and complexity contrasts sharply with the modular, practical tools needed for everyday implementation. Action is not so much needed not for design, but for implementation: provide tools to bridge the gap between theory and practice. These could empower instructors to apply what they have planned and integrate it in daily teaching routines. One has to curate a practical toolkit with micro-learning modules, editable templates, and concise implementation guides, compatible with existing support frameworks.

The cross-case analysis with further detailed findings (see Table 5) underscores the layered, context-dependent nature of EMBED's implementation and highlights pathways to enhancing its impact via EMBED+. At the programme level, EMBED has served as a reflective instrument during discussions with programme directors and teams, effectively fostering awareness and insight. However, further scaffolding is necessary to translate these reflections into concrete, structured follow-up actions and sustained change. Embedding that programme-to-course connection strengthens its practical impact and ensures EMBED+ becomes part of the pedagogical toolkit, not merely a strategic artifact. Therefore, one has to develop structured implementation pathways, enriched with case studies and change-management resources that support teams from reflection to action. While strategic conversations around vision and policy have emerged institution-wide, most of these efforts remain informal. The absence of formal embedding - through policy

documents, QA cycles, or curricular mandates - limits their lasting impact. Hence, at the institutional level, one might provide resources to formalise blended learning outcomes into policy and QA cycles.

While EMBED's breadth enabled strategic exploration and blueprint creation, its completeness often became a barrier. The users required substantial interpretation, translation, and streamlining before it could be integrated into local workflows. Consequently, institutions across Belgium and the Netherlands selectively adapted, translated, and edited the model to fit their unique language preferences, institutional types (university of applied sciences vs. research university), stakeholder roles, and strategic ambitions. Institutional barriers like time limitations, tool inflexibility (e.g., non-editable PDFs), and lack of implementation momentum further hindered uptake.

Table 5*Cross-case analysis: findings in detail*

Research question	Focus	Findings (Institutional level)	Findings (Programme level)	Findings (Course level)	Comparative insights
(1) Factors influencing adoption and implementation	Drivers, barriers, competing frameworks	Strategic urgency (COVID19) and alignment with institutional agendas were key drivers; abstractness and competing perceptions of stakeholders hindered use (R1, R3, R6).	EMBED helped define programme goals, particularly when aligned with design; limitations arose when tools a not directly tied to design practice (R2, R5).	Adoption occurred via grassroots, advisor-led initiatives such as study-load and self-regulation course interventions (R4, R7).	EMBED uptake depends on strategic context and linkage to existing frameworks; more likely to be embedded where advisors support local implementation.
(2) Stakeholder perceptions	Benefits, challenges, perceived value	EMBED was appreciated for enabling institutional dialogue and shared vision setting, yet lacked integration with QA, finance, and policy cycles (R1, R3).	Viewed as useful for setting vision and alignment, but perceived gap between maturity framework and practical design applications (R2, R5).	Useful for innovations such as self-regulation and structured guidance, especially when accompanied by support; but frustrations around vague design remained (R4, R7).	EMBED understood as conceptually powerful but needs tangible links to practice and clear guidance to avoid user confusion or disengagement.
(3) Variations across institutions	Implementation differences, contextual influences	Institutional adoption varied: some used EMBED to spark strategy, others embedded it structurally (R1, R3, R8).	Some institution-specific programmes translated EMBED into design, while others kept it as a conceptual tool (R2, R5).	Course-level roll-out varied; pockets of maturity emerged, especially where advisors facilitated focus (R4, R7, R6).	Variations reflect institutional culture, support infrastructure, and existence of advisory roles => need for flexible embedding strategies.
(4) Support for maturity of blended practices	Evidence of EMBED's contribution	EMBED triggered institutional maturity progression, facilitating vision alignment and strategic evolution (R1, R6, R8).	Enabled programme-level design activity adjustments aligned with maturity objectives (R2, R5).	Supported course-level innovation such as student self-regulation strategies and faculty readiness, particularly through advisor influence (R4, R7, R6).	EMBED contributes to maturity at all levels, but practical impact is strongest when guidance, advisory input, and design alignment are provided.
(5) Emerging needs and EMBED+ improvements	New requirements, tools, formats	Stakeholders requested subdivided institutional indicators: layered support, finance, QA, AI literacy, and sustainability (R3, R6, R8).	Desire to integrate EMBED with curriculum design workflows for stronger operational relevance (R2, R5).	Need for accessible, light, editable tools offering next-step actions, to reduce friction and encourage uptake (R4, R7).	Future EMBED+ should be modular, actionable, context-aware, and incorporate emergent themes such as AI, ethics, and structural support domains.
(6) Sustainability requirements	Policies, structures, governance	Sustainability calls for embedding EMBED into governance policies, QA regimes, PD frameworks, and infrastructural transparency (R3, R8).	Stronger alignment between institutional resources and programme needs, especially in education-finance interaction, is critical (R2, R5, R6).	Course-level sustainability depends on peer diffusion, advisor-driven implementation, and resource-aware tools (R4, R7).	Long-term success requires embedding EMBED within institutional frameworks, supported by clarity in roles, accessible tools, and communities of practice.

3.5. Key implications for EMBED+

EMBED+ should remain a multilevel framework that distinguishes maturity at the course, program and at the institution level. It allows for a clear understanding of the progression from basic to advanced stages of blended practices' implementation. It fosters strategic alignment and unified language across leadership bodies, particularly during pivots in educational strategy. The model also surfaces inconsistencies in perceived maturity, which enables more focused strategic planning and goal-setting. True maturity developed through bottom-up interventions, often by advisors or local champions. Where EMBED also became meaningful was in its pairing with existing curriculum practices. In summary, EMBED+ stands as a strategically powerful maturity framework, yet its success depends on the translation of conceptual potential into practical and context-sensitive application.

Based on the case by case and cross-case analysis of the interviews, we propose the following adjustments to the conceptual structure and theoretical dimensions of the EMBED model, modifications to EMBED's supporting tools and resources, and changes in how EMBED and its deliverables could be practically implemented and used in institutional contexts.

3.5.1. Adaptations to the model

- **Add elements of institutional support and infrastructure:** EMBED+ should address more the development of institutional policies and support structures that facilitate the adoption of blended learning practices across all levels, such as procurement policies and access to digital tools.
- **Introduce a fourth maturity level:**
 - **Digital sovereignty:** Ensuring the university retains control over its systems, such as learning platforms, data storage, and applications, rather than depending entirely on commercial vendors. This involves choosing open-source tools, hosting data locally or within compliant cloud environments, and avoiding vendor lock-in. It reflects the level of autonomy, and acknowledges institutions capable of fully managing digital sovereignty, policy autonomy, and ethical technology frameworks.
 - **Sustainable digital learning ecosystem:** Maintaining a coherent, stable, and long-term digital environment by managing platforms holistically, identifying a clear owner for the entire digital learning ecosystem (e.g., a "product owner"), and ensuring the infrastructure, governance, and resources remain reliable over time.
- **Differentiate by stakeholder:** There is a need to differentiate the core components of the EMBED+ model by stakeholder perspective (e.g., instructors, instructional designers, project teams, institutional leadership). Each requires different levels of depth, granularity, and framing when using the model. This layered use would enable the model to function as a flexible instrument, aligning strategic ambitions with operational realities.
- **Anchor abstract maturity in real-life examples:** EMBED+ gains effectiveness when theoretical maturity stages are illustrated with concrete, level-specific scenarios.
- **Allow for adaptation and localization:** EMBED+ should maintain flexibility so that institutions and educators can adapt deliverables and indicators to fit their local context, culture, and priorities.

3.5.2. Deliverable adaptations

- **Bundle with tools for institutional dialogue:** Embedding strategic change within leadership discussions is more effective when EMBED+ is paired with facilitation tools such as the “Bewegingssensor”. This combination allows for richer, more aligned conversations around institutional maturity and development goals.
- **Enhance concrete examples, practical usability:** Develop and share detailed examples of maturity implementation across different dimensions. Providing concrete examples of how to implement maturity in various dimensions can aid institutions in translating theoretical concepts into actionable practices. Create resources that illustrate the application of maturity thinking in real scenarios. The spider-diagram maturity visualization might be developed as an interactive decision support tool, enhanced with user stories, tooltips, and links to professional development opportunities.
- **Offer continuous professional development (CPD) and modular microlearning resources:** Offering professional development opportunities that focus on the practical application of the model and its deliverables, fostering a culture of continuous improvement in blended practices. EMBED+ should integrate learning analytics into CPD and QA, so that instructors benefit from training that combines pedagogical innovation with data interpretation skills. EMBED+ might also offer concise microlearning modules that improve educators’ competences.

3.5.3. Applied usage adjustments

- **Facilitate incremental implementation:** While initial resistance and logistical challenges are common, targeted interventions can facilitate smoother transitions. EMBED+ could explicitly promote a step-by-step, iterative approach to blended practice improvements, encouraging one to pick a few indicators for gradual enhancement each semester. While the users emphasized that it is more motivating and sustainable than sweeping institutional reforms, it advocates for continuous staff reflection, infrastructure, and policy alignment. Supporting this through scaffolding tools and guidance can help reduce overwhelm and increase sustained engagement.
- **Focus on training and faculty engagement:** Given reported faculty resistance and lack of training, EMBED+ should include targeted professional development resources and communities of practice that empower teachers to experiment confidently with blended learning models and tools.
- **Leverage AI and chatbots as support tools:** EMBED+ could explore expanding AI-based assistants not only as tutors but as facilitators in blended course design, perhaps by integrating adaptive feedback or personalized improvement suggestions based on EMBED indicators.
- **Design and testing mechanisms:** EMBED+ should build in systematic design and user feedback loops, to test and refine materials continuously and ensure their relevance and usability across diverse educational contexts.
- **Fortify institutional usage:** There is a clear need for layered, and simplified versions of the existing deliverables that match the needs of different stakeholder groups. It was also repeatedly highlighted that basic, editable versions would facilitate translation, simplification, and re-contextualization for different institutional needs. EMBED+ should offer rubrics, checklists, and examples for each maturity level. Additionally, establishing a repository of user cases where institutions share how they have applied and adjusted the model would enhance community learning and improve the model’s transferability.
- **Community-based usage:** Work with institutions and bodies like SURF to create shared repositories or negotiated access to blended learning technologies.

3.5.4. Prioritization of actions

The key implications mentioned can be prioritized based on their potential contribution and their feasibility of implementation. Table 6 is organised around the development of:

- the EMBED+ (conceptual framework)
- the EMBED+ Matrix (operational assessment instrument)
- the EMBED+ Hub (supporting ecosystem for community building, tools, and resources)

Importance and feasibility serve as the guiding axes for prioritization. Furthermore, the success of EMBED+ does not lie in the sophistication of the framework itself, but in how effectively the model, matrix, and hub work together to support reflective, incremental, and context-sensitive maturity development. This implies that the EMBED+ model should prioritize conceptual robustness combined with contextual flexibility, that the EMBED+ Matrix must remain practical, editable, and improvement-oriented rather than evaluative or punitive, and that the EMBED+ Hub is critical for translating conceptual potential into sustained practice through community exchange, dialogue, and shared resources.

Table 6
Prioritisation of actions for EMBED+ development

EMBED+ component	Priority action	Rationale
High importance / High feasibility		
Model	Anchor maturity stages in concrete, multilevel examples	Increases conceptual clarity and reduces abstraction; essential for adoption
Model	Strengthen links between EMBED+ and existing curriculum and QA practices	Positions EMBED+ as an enhancement, not a parallel system
Matrix	Provide editable rubrics and checklists per maturity stage	Enables localization and practical use across contexts
Matrix	Explicitly support incremental, indicator-by-indicator improvement	Aligns with bottom-up maturity development and reduces resistance
Hub	Create a shared language for strategic dialogue (e.g. guided reflection tools)	Facilitates alignment across leadership and operational stakeholders
Hub	Develop and curate real-world use cases illustrating maturity progression	Accelerates peer learning and trust in the framework
High importance / Low feasibility		
Model	Introduce a fourth maturity dimension focused on digital sovereignty	Essential for long-term sustainability, ethics, and institutional autonomy
Model	Explicitly integrate institutional support, infrastructure, and policy logic	Moves EMBED+ beyond pedagogy to full ecosystem maturity
Matrix	Align maturity indicators with institutional data and analytics structures	Enables diagnostic maturity but requires infrastructural readiness
Hub	Establish governance for a sustainable digital learning ecosystem	High strategic value, but organizationally complex
Hub	Build systematic feedback loops to iteratively refine EMBED+ tools	Ensures relevance across contexts but requires long-term commitment
Low importance / High feasibility		
Matrix	Develop standalone maturity visualisations (e.g. spider diagrams)	Useful for awareness, limited impact without facilitation
Hub	Offer generic microlearning modules on EMBED+ concepts	Helpful for onboarding but insufficient for change
Hub	Create simplified communication versions of EMBED+ deliverables	Aids dissemination, not maturity development
Low importance / Low feasibility		
Matrix	Fully automated AI-based EMBED+ self-assessment	Risks oversimplification and loss of reflective depth
Hub	Benchmark institutions solely on EMBED+ scores	Conflicts with the model's context-sensitive philosophy
Model	Enforce standardized EMBED+ implementation across all contexts	Undermines adaptability and bottom-up ownership

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